

LEVERAGING ONLINE TEACHING SCIENCE AT THE PRIMARY SCHOOLS LEVEL DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract: The COVID - 19 pandemic has profoundly affected the education process. A sudden shift to online education changed the mechanism of the education system process. It can be seen clearly that the online learning has a strong impact on improving students' performance. The primary aim of this study is to explore the experiences of participants concerning online science education at the primary school level. A qualitative research methodology was employed, utilizing interviews as the primary data collection technique. Data were gathered from primary schools located in Al Jouf province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), during the academic year 2020-2021. A purposive sampling method was applied. The results revealed that students in grades 4, 5, and 6 generally held positive views towards online instruction, largely due to their personal experiences with remote learning at home. However, there were also negative perceptions regarding online science teaching in these grades, attributed to inadequate internet access, particularly from the perspective of parents. Additionally, teachers and administrators noted a lack of demonstrative tools as a contributing factor to the negative views on science instruction in grades 4, 5, and 6. Further research is warranted to examine gender differences in academic

INTRODUCTION

ONLINE LEARNING

The 21st century has been considered the age of innovation of the World Wide Web (WWW). Instant Information and Communications Technology (ICT's), are used in many fields of knowledge such as medicine, engineering and education is no exception. It has been acknowledged that the internet in

educational arena has changed the role of teachers as well as learners, distance education provides a chance of interaction between instructors and learners either inside the classroom or outside such as a café , a library and even in office. In fact that, remote learning is used interchangeably to synchronous/ an online environment learning which means a learning process that students they no need to present to school or college , whereas, teachers can deliver courses from own home by using multi means for instance a smartphone, tablets, and the internet via many platforms, Google Classroom, and Zoom Meeting. Remote learning in times of pandemic owns an echo by providing various implications, and best practice , switch of education from face-to-face . Remote learning is growing fast and applications technologies play a crucial role that motivated many institutions adopted it widely in order to make students participate effectively. Various merits that can be observed in applying remote learning for instance promotes the creation of learning networks, fasten interaction, widen communication, and access to many platforms through mobile devices, beside that it uses network technologies to create, foster, deliver, and facilitate learning anytime and everywhere without physical barriers between participants and instructors. Interaction played an essential role in learning expansion by using various instruments, tools, mediation and applications. Electronic learning offers numerous advantages, including networks that enable immediate updates, storage, retrieval, and sharing of information, all facilitated through computers utilizing standard internet technology. The implementation of online emergency remote teaching was initiated to safeguard individuals from the risk of COVID-19 infection during the pandemic. Online education, particularly synchronous learning, encompasses more than merely delivering educational content; it constitutes an educational process that fosters learner motivation, accountability, flexibility, and choice. This study is grounded in social presence theory, which emphasizes three key interactions: student-student, student-instructor, and student-content. Recently, scholars have introduced two additional components: student-interface interaction and vicarious interaction.

ONLINE LEARNING IN SAUDI ARABIA

The Coronavirus (COVID-19) first appeared in December 2019, leading the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it a global pandemic in March 2020 (WHO, 2020). Its rapid spread across numerous countries prompted the implementation of stringent measures, including lockdowns and social distancing, while some nations opted for approaches focused on building immunity. To mitigate the transmission of the virus, various strategies were adopted, such as remote work and flexible hours, as authorities sought to prevent person-to-person infection. Consequently, public health guidelines became increasingly stringent, mandating a physical distance of approximately one meter, the use of hand sanitizers, and the wearing of masks in public spaces. Educational institutions, including schools and universities, were

compelled to suspend in-person activities, leading to the widespread adoption of emergency remote teaching. In Saudi Arabia, the outbreak of COVID-19 in March 2020 resulted in the complete suspension of classes and school-related activities as part of a public health emergency response. The government announced the cancellation of all educational activities, including training and internships, as local transmission cases continued to rise until early May 2020, coinciding with Eid al-Fitr. In response, the government sought alternative methods to address the disruption, promoting remote emergency teaching and various other educational delivery methods, such as synchronous learning (Mustafa & Mubarak, 2022).

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) has emerged as a leader in information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure within the Western Asia region, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. The educational sector in KSA has embraced e-learning across all levels of education. The country has progressively enhanced its infrastructure to support e-learning initiatives through educational and business institutions (Alfawaz & Yamin, 2020). The evolution of e-learning in KSA can be traced back to the initial implementation of closed-circuit television as a means of delivering educational content. This system provided a one-way video feed coupled with a two-way audio network to mitigate the shortage of instructors in higher education institutions (Aljaber, 2018). Notably, the educational system in KSA has advanced significantly, with King Abdulaziz University being the first institution to implement an e-learning system in 2006, utilizing Blackboard as its primary Learning Management System (LMS) (Aldiab et al., 2019; Alfawaz & Yamin, 2020). E-learning represents a dynamic environment that integrates various components of the educational process, offering extensive information and encouraging learners to acquire and share knowledge effectively (Syedam, 2014). The rapid expansion of e-learning in Saudi Arabia can be attributed to several factors, including the overwhelming demand for higher education that exceeds the available supply. Given the vast geographical area of KSA and its numerous communities, the higher education system motivates citizens to pursue their studies in diverse locations. Consequently, the advancement of e-learning has led many tertiary institutions in KSA to adopt high-quality standards, achieving accreditation from reputable US and European programs (Yamin, 2013). However, challenges remain in the realm of e-learning, including issues related to technology, resource materials, financial support, societal educational levels, the design and presentation of educational materials, as well as users' attitudes towards these solutions (Alasmari & Khan, 2014).

This section presents a review of research related to online teaching and learning in primary schools within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), as well as studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Abu Gamfi (2013), factors contributing to students' difficulties in engaging with school science include the increased demands on students' time for learning science and the less practical nature of science education, although this research was focused on the high school level. The findings indicated that both male and

female students in non-science disciplines exhibited a lack of interest in their studies. Furthermore, at the primary school level, teachers employed demonstrative and scientific methods of investigation in their science instruction. However, there was a noted deficiency in teaching skills among some parents, who primarily engaged in providing task instructions (Lashley, 2019). A similar study targeted parents and science teachers in a primary school setting, revealing that teachers reinterpreted the philosophy of distance learning and adapted their assignments to new formats, which positively impacted their students' academic performance. Parents played a crucial role in assisting their children by checking their work and helping them solve problems. Despite the challenges, the online learning format proved effective during the pandemic, leading to new trends in teaching and learning. The study highlighted the importance of collaboration among teachers, parents, and schools to enhance the effectiveness of educational methods. It was noted that teachers designed learning frameworks that considered students' backgrounds, including family income and specific needs during the COVID-19 period (Kvavadze, 2020).

A similar study indicated that educators who are dedicated to maintaining communication with students' parents have implemented new learning methods and assigned tasks while providing immediate feedback to their students. In contrast, the Ministry of Education in Al Jouf Province, Saudi Arabia, responded promptly by suspending face-to-face teaching and physical attendance. Since March 13, 2020, the Al Jouf educational authority has emphasized that students are not permitted to attend schools. This decision was made by the Saudi government as a preventive measure against the spread of COVID-19. Subsequently, Al Jouf initiated online classes on August 16, 2020, and adopted remote science teaching for primary school students. However, teaching primary pupils via the internet has proven to be particularly challenging for grades 4, 5, and 6, especially considering the absence of physical laboratories and the limited time of 30 minutes per period to cover both theoretical and practical tasks. Quizzes have revealed a weak academic performance and highlighted issues related to internet connectivity.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study was carried out with the following objectives:

1-To ascertain in perspective science teachers regarding the instruction of science to students in grades 4,5, and 6 through online platform at elementary primary schools located in Al Jouf governorate - in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

2- To assess attitudes schools' principals toward online teaching science to grades 4, 5, and 6 at the elementary schools in Al Jouf governorate - in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

3- To ascertain parental perspective toward implementation of online science education to grades 4,5, and 6 at the elementary schools in Al Jouf governorate - in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

4- To ascertain the students perspective on the utilization of online education for teaching science to students in grades 4, 5, and 6 in elementary schools located in Al Jouf governorate - in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

CONCLUSION

The Youth Self-Report (YSR/11-18) remains a valuable tool in assessing behavioral and emotional problems among adolescents, particularly when combined with the multi-informant approach. As globalization and cultural shifts continue to influence adolescent development, it becomes increasingly important to consider the socio-cultural context in which adolescents navigate their mental health challenges. Arab adolescents in Israel face unique pressures, including the tension between traditional values and modern influences, which contribute to a higher prevalence of eating disorders and psychological distress. Moreover, sleep quality, which plays a critical role in adolescent well-being, continues to be an area of concern, particularly in light of recent global disruptions.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research-phenomenological approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of participants' perceptions regarding the teaching of science at the primary school level during the COVID-19 pandemic. It aims to elucidate the significance of individuals' lived experiences and to explore in depth the phenomenon as experienced by those directly involved (Creswell, 2014).

PARTICIPANTS AND ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This research focused on the lived experiences of four groups: pupils, science teachers, the principal, and parents. It was conducted at a primary school in Al Jouf province, Saudi Arabia, during the COVID-19 pandemic, specifically examining online science teaching that commenced in August and continued until mid-December 2020. Ethical considerations were prioritized, including the selection of participants who voluntarily agreed to take part. However, science teachers and pupils were not informed prior to the interviews, as they interacted with the researcher in a daily online setting. Participants were purposefully selected, with some being contacted face-to-face, such as a science teacher and the school principal. The interviews were structured around open-ended questions. Additionally, the researcher ensured that participants received adequate information regarding the study's objectives. Throughout the interview process, participants were repeatedly reminded of the study's aims. Another ethical consideration involved coding the actual names of participants to maintain their confidentiality; for example,

principals of Al-Qimam International Schools were coded as (P), women as (W), men as (M), science teachers as (T), and pupils as (PS). The researcher was committed to keeping all information confidential to protect privacy. During the interviews, data were recorded using a mobile phone, with an emphasis on detailed and precise information. To safeguard the integrity of the data, all information was documented and recorded meticulously, with transcription focusing on every single word. Validity and reliability assessments were performed by experts in this study. Out of a total of 37 students, 6 were selected to represent grades 4, 5, and 6. However, only 3 of these students consented to participate in the questionnaire and were actively involved in online science classes conducted via Google Zoom during the academic session of 2020-2021.

The interview was planned to span a minimum of two days, with each session lasting five minutes, occurring between October 2020 and November 2020, to achieve the objectives of this study. The researcher collected data directly by conducting interviews with participants via Google Zoom. In accordance with Islamic principles and cultural norms, women were excluded from this study. Google Zoom was utilized to facilitate a group discussion regarding the Biology periods. The interviews were conducted during the scheduled break period, specifically aimed at the students. A second interview was held in person with the principal science teacher and the parents. The participants included three boys, with an average age of 9 to 10 years; two men, with an average age of 50 to 59 years; the principal, with an average age of 58 years; and science teachers, with an average age of 50 to 56 years. The characteristics of the participants were homogeneous, all residing in Sakaka city and enrolled at Al-Qimam International Schools, boys' section. The interviews were conducted in English.

INSTRUMENTATION

Interview questions were designed by the researcher and were categorized into three main themes and their respective subthemes:

Theme 1: Teaching science challenges

Theme 2: The internet coverage barriers

Theme 3: Learning at Home

Two distinct components were employed concerning the interview questions. The first segment focused on interviewing participants, including the principal, parents, and the science teacher. The second segment involved the formulation of interview questions specifically aimed at evaluating the knowledge of students in grades 4, 5, and 6 who were engaged in a Biology curriculum. Before the interviews were conducted, professionals in the field of education assessed the validity and reliability of the questions.

FINDINGS

The data of this study have been transcribed in word program; pertaining to the analyses and the result was formed through a transparent interview. There are three major themes that have been shaded participants' experiences toward science teaching in an online learning environment at the primary schools level at AlQimam International Schools at Al Jouf province - KSA, can be categorized into three main themes are the following: 1- Difficulties encountered in Teaching science. 2-Limitations to the internet accessibility 3- Home based education. The following are the specific themes analyzed within the framework a phenomenological approach .

Theme1: Difficulties encountered in Teaching science

This theme showed several participants' experiences within teaching online science at the elementary schools' level . Participants point of views are the following:

T1: Teaching science has two parts, theoretical part and applied explanations for pupils.

PS1: Really, "we need a tangible laboratory to avoid theoretical teaching in terms of Biology classes".

PS2: I faced difficulties in understanding some of the science classes, especially Biology terminologies".

PS3: I think, "Online interaction with the science teacher helpful to understand online Biology classes".

T1: Online science classes and interaction with pupils is very fruitful for learning a lot of Biology terms".

P1: For me, "Online teaching science is so useful but, the practical part is absent ".

M1: I'm not satisfied enough from absence of the practice and labs in Biology class ".

PS3: I think, "The time given to science classes is not enough ".

M1: There is no doubt that online teaching classes are better than traditional classes because pupils can move freely and even have a chance to record.

PS2: Yes, "teacher of science wastes time in Biology within the introduction and conclusion".

Based on the perspectives of the participants, it is evident that their responses reflected a range of experiences regarding the challenges of teaching science at Al-Qimam International Schools in Al Jouf province, KSA. Both parents, the principal, science teachers, and students expressed a mix of positive and negative views about online science education. For instance, some parents felt that the time allocated for Biology classes was insufficient. Conversely, while some parents viewed science education as beneficial, the principal acknowledged that although students had opportunities to document their learning, the lack of hands-on practice might lead to dissatisfaction among pupils. The science teacher conveyed a positive outlook, stating that "Teaching science encompasses both theoretical components and practical

explanations for students at this grade level." However, it was noted that some students displayed a lack of interest in online science classes, which may be attributed to prolonged periods of confinement at home. These findings align with the research conducted by Yamin (2013), Alasmari & Khan (2014), Lozano et al (2021), Daniela & Visvizi (2022), and Azizah (et al 2021).

Theme 2: Limitations to the internet accessibility

This theme showed various participants' experiences toward online teaching science at the primary schools level. Participants point of views are the following:

M1: Definitely, Online classes assist pupils to manage time but there is a problematic of the internet service".

T1: Lagging during Biology class increased pupils anxiety and even I “.

P1:” the internet service lagging happens as a result of over loading in the server at the school but we have a plan to solve it”.

PS1: Of course, “Online science classes had helped me in terms of saving time and effort.”

PS2: “I prefer online science classes and a comfortable place at my home but sometimes I missed beginning of classes.

PS3: “I would like to have a conducive room at home for attending online science classes and provide with a good Wifi device.

T1: Definitely, “Online science classes put a lot of pressure on me such as logging in and out.”

M1: “the internet disconnection sometimes missing pupils a part of the class. Cut off online science classes waste our pupils time.

This section presents the experiences of participants regarding the teaching of online Biology classes at AlQimam International Schools in Al Jouf province, KSA. It appears that parents, the principal, science teachers, and students expressed varying opinions. Some parents viewed the teaching of science as beneficial; however, they noted issues with internet connectivity. The principal also expressed the need for an upgrade to the school's internet infrastructure. Students reported that "the Wi-Fi server sometimes disrupted our focus during science classes." The lagging internet connection was attributed to overload, and the science teacher shared negative views about the internet coverage, highlighting that disruptions during Biology classes heightened students' anxiety. Additionally, parents expressed dissatisfaction with the internet service, stating that "online classes helped students manage their time, but the internet issues were problematic." Overall, the perceptions of participants reflect both positive and negative aspects of teaching online Biology classes at AlQimam International Schools in Al Jouf province, KSA. These findings align with the research conducted by Yamin in 2013 and Alasmari & Khan in 2014.

Theme 3: Home based education

This theme showed different experiences of participants toward teaching Biology in an online classes at the primary schools level. All participants point of views are the following:

T1: I used various tools attract pupils during the online teaching biology classes such as photos and illustrations even textbook.”

M1: Really, “our pupils benefitted from online interaction teaching biology classes”.

PS1: I agree that,” online interactive classes are attractive but, there is limitations the laboratory “.

PS2: “I would like interactive online Biology classes with instructor and colleagues “.

PS1: “Online science Biology classes are interested and I motivated from the instructor”.

PS3:“an appropriate place at home feels me comfort to follow online science class seriously”.

The feedback from participants indicates a mix of positive and negative experiences regarding online science education for grades 4, 5, and 6 at Al-Qimam International Schools in Al Jouf province, KSA. Participants expressed both favorable and unfavorable perceptions for various reasons. For instance, students reported positive sentiments, stating that "the comfort of my home provides an appropriate environment to engage seriously in online science classes," and added, "I find online science classes engaging, especially with the motivation provided by our instructor." Similarly, parents noted, "Our children have truly benefited from the interactive nature of online biology classes." Furthermore, the online biology instructor remarked, "I employed various tools to engage students during online biology lessons, including models, illustrations, and even the textbook." Overall, participants exhibited positive perceptions towards online biology instruction, aligning with findings from Yamin (2013), Alasmari & Khan (2014), Lozano et al. (2021), Daniela & Visvizi (2022), and Azizah et al. (2021).

CONCLUSION

Primary data revealed the perceptions of parents, the principal, science teachers, and students. The results indicated both negative and positive attitudes towards online science education for grades 4, 5, and 6, thereby corroborating findings from similar studies conducted in other African and Asian nations. Students expressed positive views regarding online science instruction in grades 4, 5, and 6, attributing this to the conducive learning environment at home. Conversely, negative perceptions were noted concerning online science classes, primarily due to issues related to internet connectivity. Further research is essential to investigate gender differences in anxiety and satisfaction within an online learning context, particularly regarding the academic performance of male and female students in science education in Al Jouf province in Saudi Arabia. However, the conclusions drawn from this study are limited in their applicability due to the narrow focus on a private primary school's boys division.

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